

Design as a competitive advantage for businesses and its influence on consumers' purchasing decision-making processes: a perspective from Brazilian designers and entrepreneurs

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ABSTRACT

This research focused on understanding design as a competitive advantage in business and how it connects consumers and companies. First, the study offers a review of design, business strategy, and consumer psychology literature. Second, qualitative research was carried out through 10 interviews with opinion leaders in the field of Brazilian design. The collected data were examined using content analysis. The results revealed that people-centered design significantly influences companies' success. Additionally, design attributes are associated with emotions, intelligence, project, and thinking. Finally, the interviewees' perspectives and the literature revealed that design has a strong capacity to influence consumers and build brand loyalty

KEYWORDS: Design. Strategy. Business. Consumer.

INTRODUCTION

All over the world, companies from all sectors have sought to develop through innovation in order to achieve sustainable results and guarantee their economic development and perpetuation in the markets. Design and innovation are increasingly present on the business agenda, as not only sources of profit, but also in their ability to provide solutions to everyday human problems and to differentiate their businesses and brands. More than selling products and offering services, successful organizations promote unique experiences for consumers, adding real value to their goods.

Two major discoveries are cited by Verganti (2009) in his book: the first concerns radical innovations, which are undoubtedly one of the greatest sources of competitive

advantage for companies in the long term. The second tells us that people don't buy products, but meanings. In the field of marketing research and consumer behavior, many researchers have endeavored to explore the topic of consumption and how consumers react to the meaning of products and how they make the decision or not to purchase a particular good. It has increasingly been observed that these consumers react to symbolism, meanings and cultural factors in their decision-making process for purchasing goods and services.

The main purpose of this study was to understand how it is possible to establish a competitive edge in business through design and how the use of this strategy can connect businesses to consumers, influencing the decision-making process when purchasing their goods and services. The objectives were to understand how companies can direct their strategies to develop a culture focused on design, how design can connect companies and consumers and, finally, how consumers are really touched by the goods and services offered/produced by companies.

The proposed methodology takes a qualitative approach to analysis, using descriptive, explanatory and exploratory techniques. Firstly, a theoretical review of the literature on Design, Business Strategy, Marketing and Consumer Psychology. Secondly, a field survey, based on 10 (ten) interviews. Among those interviewed were designers, *CEOs* and company or business leaders, all opinion leaders whose experience and mastery of the subject is relevant within the ecosystem surveyed. The data collected in the interviews was analyzed, categorized, summarized and consolidated. In this context, the content analysis technique was applied to the interviews, in order to correlate the data collected with the assumptions of the study and with the theoretical framework used. The purpose of the content analysis was to critically explore and understand the meaning of design, its influence on business and its relationship with consumers, in the view of the experts interviewed. An analysis by category and frequency of terms was adopted.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The current business model has seen ever-increasing levels of competition between markets, and consumers have become even more demanding in their choice processes. In this way, the topic in question has become extremely pertinent and relevant to studies in the field of Business Administration. The continuity and development of companies increasingly depends on understanding the need for differentiation and innovation in order to achieve sustainable business growth and perpetuity for their brands. Driessen (2006) draws attention to the need for companies to seek innovation rather than competition for costs, in addition to

the recent human phenomenon, which has altered consumption patterns towards a model of seeking emotions and sensitivity:

In recent years, the amount of literature on the dematerialization of the economy seems to have multiplied exponentially. Evidently, we are entering an era in which we will get rid of the 'things' that we learned to produce so efficiently during the industrial and information eras. In a sense, we're just moving one step up Maslow's pyramid. Our material prosperity and abundance is giving rise to a phenomenon that places greater value on "right-brain" sensibilities such as beauty, well-being, spirituality and emotion. At the same time, competition (mainly from Asia) is knocking on the door of our industrialized Western countries. If we can no longer compete on costs, what will our next innovation platform look like? (Driessen, 2006, p. 61).

Stevens (2010) describes that the role of design as a differentiation strategy for companies has now become much more important due to the globalization of trade. Many studies and scientific research have been carried out in recent years looking at the correlation between the themes of design as a competitive strategy for companies and how this connects with the decision-making process when consumers choose goods and services. The idea of design as a strategic resource for companies is much more than adding value in order to sell more or increase profit margins.

It is increasingly recognized in industry and empirical literature that design contributes strategically to companies pursuing other strategies—not just manufacturers, but all types of business—in ways beyond the conception and modeling of a product. Design can help create and develop a company's relationship with its customers, end users and other stakeholders, meeting and exceeding their needs and desires; it can help drive and exploit innovation, expand or redefine a market and can be applied within the company to improve processes, working environments and communications. These are all established and increasingly accepted design capabilities." (Stevens, 2010, p. 1).

The value and importance of design for a company has become recognized in recent decades. In 1984, Kotler and Rath urged business leaders to revise their vision of design far beyond a cosmetic and decorative task applied late in development. Instead, they recognized how design could optimize customer satisfaction, company profitability, product improvement, the environment, communications and their own identity (Stevens, 2010). Another relevant line of research has examined design as an organizational resource capable of influencing firm performance (Monteiro, 2021).

Product design has been increasingly recognized as an important strategic tool, responsible for the success of leading brands such as *Apple and BMW*, as well as a tactical tool with which niche brands can differentiate themselves from competitors. Studies have shown that optimizing product design can ensure the successful launch of new products and

the continued market success of existing products (Fenko; Van Rompay, 2018). The importance of perception management in management decisions gives design its relevance in management knowledge. The value of design is the main perceived value; the perception of value translated into management jargon is the construction of a company's competitive advantage through a differentiated offer perceived in the market (Mozota, 2006a).

By changing the view of design from "project-based" to "knowledge-based", new applications for the value of design have emerged in management science. The success of *Apple*, the examples of companies like *Procter & Gamble* and *Décathlon*, which have changed their culture and integrated design into the company's *DNA*, mean that more *CEOs* are thinking about design not from the point of view of results, but from the point of view of the challenges facing contemporary managers who can turn to design *thinking* for solutions and to create new forms of governance. Suddenly, design is "a must" for business performance (Mozota, 2006a).

There is clearly an opportunity for all manufacturers to leverage the connection between design, emotions and profit margins. This would require an understanding of the design principles that govern consumers' relative preferences and purchasing decisions, depending on their wants and needs. Responses to aesthetic designs can also be related to the level of sensation-seeking, i.e. a tendency to engage in certain behaviors in order to increase sensory stimulation. However, brands can not only signal a certain level of quality, but also serve to communicate a set of symbolic values or a personality that can help forge a bond between the consumer and the brand (Landwehr; Wentzel; Herrmann, 2012).

From the perspective of consumer-oriented product design, Fenko and Van Rompay (2018) tell us that this process is the result of joint efforts and collaboration between researchers, designers, developers and marketing professionals. Consumer researchers and marketers focus on the effects of product design on a wide range of consumer responses, including aesthetic appreciation, product experience, symbolic meaning and customer satisfaction. They aim to answer the following research question: how does product design influence consumers? Through cognitive processes such as interpretation, memory retrieval and associations, consumers are able to recognize metaphors, attribute personality or other expressive characteristics and evaluate the personal or symbolic meaning of products. Emotional experience is related to affective responses to the product, such as happiness, boredom or annoyance (Fenko; Van Rompay, 2018).

The concept established by Norman and Ortony (2003) and Norman (2004) indicates that consumers make their initial judgment about the product through their aesthetic experience and this judgment can have an impact on the overall evaluation of the product's performance. In other words, attractive things seem to work better (Norman; Ortony, 2003). Furthermore, it is widely assumed that aesthetic designs trigger positive consumer responses, including an immediate desire to own the product.

Verganti's (2009) idea tells us that a product aims to satisfy customers' needs in terms of utility and functionality, while the product's sense of meaning, emotions and symbolism aim to satisfy its affective and socio-cultural roots. The way sensory stimuli impact on the affective experience of human beings has been the subject of much scientific research and empirical studies into consumer behavior. Many studies have shown the relevant importance of the symbolic meaning of products with regard to the consumer's decision-making process and the development of impressions about the brands behind these products.

A consumer's buying behavior is influenced by cultural, social, personal and psychological factors. Most of these factors are uncontrollable and beyond the hands of marketers, but they must be considered while trying to understand the complex behavior of consumers (Pawar; Naranje, 2016). Consumers' visual attention to products has become a key element in the research developed, resulting in different experimental formats for analyzing visual attention, employing different variables such as consumer motivations, familiarity with the brand, involvement with the product, recall, recognition and visual complexity (Ladeira; Nardi; Santini; Jardim, 2019).

The ultimate measure of effective design is the overall consumer experience it offers. Hedonic benefits are defined as those pertaining to aesthetic and experiential benefits, while utilitarian benefits are defined as those pertaining to instrumental and functional benefits (Chitturi, 2009). Kotler and Keller (2006) define that companies are responsible for the design of their products, with the aim of achieving differentiation, communicating their benefits and attracting the consumer to identify with the need or desire, achieving satisfaction.

Aesthetics increase consumers' willingness to pay more by enhancing three types of perceived benefits: functional confidence, experiential emotion and self-expressive pride. Specifically, good aesthetics improve anticipatory perception and promote emotions of confidence, excitement and pride. Previous research has shown that customers are willing to pay more for hedonic benefits than utilitarian benefits (Chitturi, 2018). In conclusion to her research, the author reports that:

The main insights provided by this research are: 1) improved aesthetics enhances the perceived functional benefits offered by the product, leading to a greater anticipated feeling of trust; 2) superior aesthetics enhances the perceived experiential benefits offered by the product, leading to a greater anticipated feeling of excitement; 3) superior aesthetics improves the perceived self-expressive benefits, leading to a greater anticipated feeling of pride; 4) these enhanced feelings of confidence, excitement and pride significantly influence customers' willingness to pay; and, 5) improving self-expression benefits by improving aesthetic pride leads to a greater increase in willingness to pay than improving experiential benefits by improving aesthetic excitement and aesthetic confidence. The results of this research show that superior aesthetics improve feelings of functional confidence, experiential emotion and self-expressive pride, leading to a greater willingness to pay. In conclusion, we have shown how and why good aesthetics is a great business (Chitturi, 2018, p. 224).

The appearance of a product can have aesthetic and symbolic value for consumers, communicate functional characteristics and give an impression of quality (functional value) and communicate ease of use (ergonomic value) (Creusen; Schoormans, 2005). Numerous findings in the *New Product Development* (NPD) literature have shown that products that are able to communicate specific meanings—through interactivity, consumer engagement and the ability to differentiate themselves from existing or competing technology—create competitive advantage for companies (Parkman, 2018).

The approach of the *World Design Organization* (WDO) definition frees design from a partial and imprecise association with the arts, which frames it only from the point of view of creating meaning through form (Patrocínio; Filgueiras; Nunes, 2022). These authors, in turn, invite us to see design as something dematerializing, transferring the importance of things to experiences. Consumer behavior is therefore a complex process that involves activities in which individuals engage when searching for, choosing, buying, using, evaluating and discarding products and services with the aim of satisfying needs, desires and aspirations (Fontgalland, 2021).

FIELD RESEARCH AND ANALYSIS METHODOLOGY

The field research collected primary data through individual interviews with experts and authorities on the subject. Qualitative research is concerned with the level of reality that cannot be quantified, i.e. it works with the universe of meanings, motivations, aspirations, beliefs, values and attitudes (Minayo, 2014).

In summary, the methodological framework for this research was as follows:

- Ten interviews were carried out, including with designers, *CEOs* and company or business leaders, all of whom are opinion formers whose experience and mastery of the subject is relevant within the ecosystem being researched.

- The sample included five *CEOs* of design production companies, four *CDOs* of large design offices and one *product director*.
- The interviews were carried out in Rio de Janeiro over the months of May, June and July 2023, through online meetings with six interviewees and four face-to-face interviews.
- The methodology applied was based on qualitative analysis, of a descriptive, explanatory and exploratory nature.
- Semi-structured interviews were used, which were more flexible and natural in their responses, combining open and closed questions, where the interviewer had the chance to explore and delve deeper into the proposed topic.
- The purpose of the interviews was to enable the results of the sample to be correlated with the data gathered from the scientific articles and bibliographies researched, with the aim of grounding the research together with empirical data on the ecosystem, the subject of this study, and relating particular aspects of the field researched to broader contexts.

In this context, the content analysis technique was applied to the interviews conducted in order to correlate the data collected with the study's assumptions. The content analysis of this research followed Bardin's (2016) idea of semantic approximations. The repetition of terms and expressions used by the participants was analyzed and then categorized and separated into blocks that could express approximations of ideas—synonyms and semantics—in order to measure the recurrence and intensity with which these expressions were presented. A system of categories is valid if it can be applied accurately to the set of information and be productive in terms of inferences.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

The depth and application of the interviews made it possible to understand the levels of perception of each actor, within the context in which design is used and applied, in its multiple aspects and strands. In the interviews, the topic was explored within the strategy of the proposed categories: Design, Business and Consumption.

The selection of participants consisted of 10 (ten) interviewees who work in the field of design, but in ecosystems that relate to the research categories in different ways. Five (5) designers of great professional relevance who represent the DESIGN category were interviewed. In addition, 4 (four) managers of companies that produce and market products

with a focus on design, who represent the BUSINESS category. Finally, 1 (one) business manager was interviewed who has a *marketplace* format, a space with stores that offer design products and receive customers, representing the CONSUMPTION category in this proposal.

The proposed interview script subdivided the questions into blocks of categories, in which the interviewees were able to freely explain and expand on their perceptions and experiences regarding the central theme of this research: design as a link between businesses and consumers. From this perspective, the interviews made it possible to explore the topic from the point of view of professionals with great experience and depth, who have been living in and exploring the design ecosystem for decades. All the interviewees have more than 10 (ten) years of experience in managing and using design as a pillar in their businesses, and from these testimonies, it was possible to establish and infer various conclusions relevant to the research.

The basic script of the interviews that support this research was divided into three blocks: 2 (two) questions related to design and its essence, 3 (three) questions that correlate design and business and 2 (two) questions that correlate design and consumption.

In the first block of interviews, in which the topic focused on defining the concept of design and its essence for people, 100% (one hundred percent) of the responses were positive when asked if design is for all people. The ten (10) interviewees categorically answered "yes". In a study on the perception of product appearance, Blijlevens, Creusen and Schoormans (2009) say that the attributes tested in various product categories proved to be stable in different consumer groups, indicating that perceptions are universal and not specific to a single class or social level.

Regarding the question about the core of design, which was proposed in a broad and freeway, when the interviewees were asked about their particular definition of design, it was interesting to see that most of the definitions followed patterns that point to design as expressions of feelings, transformation, viability and connection. Mozota (2006b) also defined design in his research with similar adjectives, in which, in his perception, design became the basis of a value model as differentiating, integrating and transforming.

Figure 1 symbolically illustrates a categorization and consolidation of the terms most cited by the interviewees to define the concept of design and the recurrence of appearances in the answers. The words were grouped by similarity of meaning or because they represented synonyms.

Figure 1: Recurrence of words and synonyms

Source: Prepared by the authors.

It is interesting to note that some definitions recurred in most of the interviewees' answers when asked about the definition of the term "design". 70% of the interviewees mentioned the word "form", which appeared redundantly throughout their answers. The term "thought" and its derivations, such as "thinking", also appeared in 40% of the answers. Other terms such as "design" or "project", as well as "transform" and "intelligence", were also repeated numerous times, with a lesser degree of intensity.

"Design is a way of thinking [...] at a certain point in evolution, man starts to use tools and so, ever since man has been man, he transforms the inputs, the raw materials, the parts and pieces that he finds. [...] And design, for me, is exactly this activity of transforming what we find, what we have access to, the resources we have available into products or spaces or even experiences." **Interviewee 1**

The next stage of the interview block - in which the questions turn to design as a company strategy, guiding business and acting as a kind of link with consumers—brought very interesting insights into the experiences and multifaceted perceptions of the interviewees. It was interesting to see how these testimonies were in line with the various studies and

research carried out in the field of design as a business strategy. Design, when understood and used correctly, can bring great competitive advantages to businesses.

Jindal, Sarangee, Echambadi and Lee (2016) report that design has been recognized as a critical source of competitive advantage and has therefore become a significant topic of examination for many scholars. Evidence of the impact of various design dimensions on market share has helped to validate how this way of thinking can be used as a strategic lever for companies. Companies are now moving beyond employing design only as a step in the product development process, but also to investing in design as a strategic tool (Jindal *et al.*, 2016).

There was almost unanimity in the reports that design, when used as a strategy designed and developed with customers in mind, brings competitive advantages to the business, resulting in higher margins, revenues and perpetuation. When established in this way, design becomes a provider of differentiation, of unique experiences, of human-centered solutions, generating a chain of values for the brand and a high perception by the market as a whole. In the opinion of 100% (one hundred percent) of those interviewed, design is a powerful source of connection between people and businesses.

When asked about the profile of design-led businesses, the interviewees replied that design-led companies are those that promote differentiation, that have their strategies centered on providing solutions for human beings, and that this vision will be able to generate advantages for the business and strengthen this link with the brand's consumers.

"When you put the human at the center, that consumer, those people you're visualizing [...] then a design, a business guided by design, involves issues of brand, culture, the functionality of products and services, the improvement of various aspects that we need, human. This design-driven business has a lot to do with innovation, attractiveness, competitiveness, social issues, human and psychological issues, in short, so design has this holistic aspect of looking at all these aspects, not just technical, engineering, marketing, but also other aspects that, often, we don't even master [...]." **Interviewee 2**

With regard to the prospect of implementing a design strategy in a business, it was interesting to note that 60% (sixty percent) of those interviewed associated this movement with a way of thinking, the implementation of a culture, a substantial change in the vision of what you want to do and where you want to go.

The purpose of finalizing the interview script was to assess, from the interviewees' point of view, design's ability to connect and influence consumers in the process of choosing goods and services, as well as to build consumer loyalty with businesses and brands that exploit design as a form of strategic thinking. When asked about design's ability to influence the purchasing decision process, the answers were unanimous. 100% (one hundred percent) of those interviewed answered that "yes, definitely" design influences their decision-making process.

An interesting variation in the answer to this question occurred in the testimony of one of the interviewees, where, despite understanding that there is influence, the report tells us that this influence also corresponds to the possibility of the consumer being able to show this purchased good or service to other people. The fact that this object or service can be shown or exposed to others makes the influence even more decisive at the time of purchase. In the story in question, the interviewee recounted an experience in her business, where a comparison is made between an object that is displayed in a "public" place in the house—a dining room—and another object that is kept in a more private place—a closet. In this case, it can be inferred that the influential power of design will be more decisive for products that can be seen or shown off than for products that are not perceived as much by others. This revelation is interesting because it shows that the perception of design also affects feelings of vanity, pride, hedonism, superiority and status.

"It does, but there are certain limits [...] [so] we launched a box, a box with a design [...], and then it didn't sell. Why? Because people pay more for a chair with a design, but for the box that they think is beautiful, that everyone thought was fabulous, they wouldn't buy... so we started to see the limit, to develop the perception of the limit [...], so it has to do with the chair being in the middle of the house and the box being stored in the closet."

Interviewee 3.

Studies confirm that the design of a product is an important factor in consumers' first impressions, and it has significant influences on behaviors such as purchasing decisions, as well as relating aesthetic design to the pleasure of looking at a product, but not to its usefulness. Based on these sequential relationships, the attitude towards design is considered emotional and is highly related to aesthetic responses (Kim; Sim; Hahm, 2014).

On the question relating design to consumer loyalty to a particular brand, the interviewees were also unanimous: 100% (one hundred percent) of the answers were to the effect that design has the ability to attract consumers, generate fans and develop evangelists

for the brand. From this perspective, it is possible to correlate the degree of consumer loyalty to brands that opt for differentiation through design. The answers included terms such as "religion", "club", "symbols" and "pride" to define this sense of belonging among consumers and their frequent choice of certain brands. Apple was an example constantly cited as a source of *loyalty* and fan generation.

"Certainly, it (design) has the power to awaken in human beings a desire to have [...]; they (consumers) are willing to commit 20 installments to be able to have that phone, in other words, they are more concerned with form than function. [...]. I've had that brand [...] since (I was) a child, have you ever stopped to think? [...] you go to the store, you can buy a coat [...] for 60 reais [...], but you'll want to buy the one for 200 reais because it has the brand (you want)." **Interviewee 4**

"Our customers are often our ambassadors. And I think that comes a lot from this relationship between brand and consumer. And I think that influences this relationship a lot, because people feel seen, because it's a product that was made for them, you know? Not by a brand that simply wants their money [...]." **Interviewee 5**

"This is so common and so surprising, people's passion for brands. I think we have a clear example of the most latent passion for a brand, which is soccer. People are passionate about the brand, the team [...], it has a lot to do with symbols. [...] The power of symbols for people enters our psychological sphere and ends up becoming part of us." **Interviewee 6.**

"He (the consumer) trusts, he likes the product, he's proud to say (that he has one). [...] So, take KitchenAid, that KitchenAid mixer, I have 3 or 4 friends who have never used it in their lives, they use it as a statue [...] to decorate their kitchen." **Interviewee 7.**

"I think so [...], a very strong example of this is Apple [...], the first thing that comes to mind is Apple. [...] The experience, the design [...] the very beautiful object, very different from the others [...], you want to be in that group [...], everyone uses it [...], there's the tribe [...]." **Interviewee 8.**

Park and Chang (2022) tell us that brands are one of the most powerful forces shaping the lives of human beings. They act as true relationship partners with consumers, providing a sense of belonging and helping them to build, express and affirm their own desired identities. This view backs up many of the answers given in this block of interviews, helping to understand and elucidate the theme: brands as symbols of expression of individual identities and the power they carry as agents that reflect consumers' personalities.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The main objective of this study was to research and understand the theme of design as a positive factor influencing businesses and their relationship with consumers. There is a wide range of literature available on the subject, as well as many scientific studies and great authors who have been researching the field for many years. Through qualitative research, we investigated the vision of major Brazilian designers and entrepreneurs who work in the production of products or explore the field of design. By cross-referencing the data from the qualitative research with the existing scientific literature, it was possible to correlate the results in a fairly consistent way, supporting the discussion and making it possible to find the answers to the purpose of the research.

In the block studying the concept and scope of design, it was interesting to note how the interviewees, in most cases, related the concept to emotions, intelligence, design and thought, also referencing the existing literature in this field of research (Mozota, 2006b; Chitturi, 2008; 2009; 2015; 2018; Demir, 2008; Margolin, 2009; Norman; Ortony, 2003; Norman, 2004; Mortati; Villari; Maffei, 2014).

Regarding the scope of design, there was unanimity in the interviewees' responses, with 100% being positive about how comprehensive design could be. Thinking about the *Apple* case, constantly cited by the interviewees, makes us realize the magnitude and depth of the inclusion of design, even when we know that it is a brand of products with relatively high prices.

Batra, Seifert and Brei (2015) tell us that the modern design process begins by observing people, investing time in understanding and developing a deep appreciation for the underlying issues. The product development and testing process can be much more centered on the benefits-experience-emotion triad than purely centered on attributes (Chitturi, 2009).

With regard to the strategy of companies that have design as a pillar, the responses correlating this strategy with the ability to differentiate, the promotion of solutions and a human-centered focus were recurrent and unanimous. There is a vast literature that endorses

and confirms these same views (Battistella; Biotto; De Toni, 2012; Homburg; Schwemmler; Kuehnl, 2015; Noble; Kumar, 2008; 2010). Thus, the research suggests that companies seeking or wishing to develop their strategies centered on design should comply with these premises, whose strategic thinking should be based on the ability to differentiate themselves and focus their attention on consumer needs and solutions. We have observed that crossing the principles of management and design thinking in the strategy domain has remarkable potential (Battistella; Biotto; De Toni, 2012). In addition, several studies have shown evidence that there is a positive relationship between investing in design and better business results (Rocco; Selinšek, 2019).

Several findings were made in a brilliant study produced by the consultancy *McKinsey & Company* (2018), under the title "*The Business Value of Design*":

We tracked the design practices of 300 publicly traded companies over a five-year period in various countries and industries. Senior managers and design leaders were interviewed or surveyed. Our team has collected more than two million pieces of financial data and recorded more than 100,000 design actions. Advanced regression analysis revealed the 12 actions that show the highest correlation with improved financial performance and grouped these actions into four broad themes (McKinsey & Company, 2018, p. 3).

A strong correlation was found between high scores on the MDI (*McKinsey Design Index*) and superior business performance. Companies have increased their revenues and total returns to shareholders (TRS) substantially faster than their counterparts in competing industries. The superior financial performance of the companies was true in the three sectors studied. In short, the potential for design-led growth is immense, both in product and service-based sectors (McKinsey & Company, 2018).

Finally, the part of the survey that concerns design's ability to act as an influencing factor in the connection between businesses and consumers also had very aligned responses. 100% of those interviewed not only believe, but affirm that design has this capacity to connect and influence the decision-making process, taking into account that they all cited real, empirical examples from their personal experiences in the field studied. The literature is also vast in this area, in which several researchers have empirically attested to how design has the ability to influence consumers, to connect them and make them loyal to brands (Hsu; Chen; Yang; Lin; Liu, 2018); Barngrover, 2005; Nam; Carnie; Bruce, 2014; Rubera, 2015). This is also a topic that deserves a lot of thought and attention from companies and entrepreneurs, as investment in implementing a design culture can transform the relationship between brands and consumers.

As for the limits, within the reality of this study, only in a qualitative research with a non-probability sample, in which the interviewees chosen are part of the same professional cycle as the researcher and the researcher himself works in the field of design, biases may have been established that are part of the culture in which the actors are inserted and, therefore, their vision may exert some level of influence on this research. In addition, there were no interviews or field tests with end consumers, only scientific articles and literature were observed on this topic, bringing only a partial view to the study. Although the study is comprehensive in terms of design, the focus of the research was on the design of physical and commercial products, giving little or no depth to the design of services, experiential, digital, complex equipment, constructions, projects, among others. Finally, this research also had limitations in terms of theoretical, practical and methodological aspects, which were limited to a thematic approach to design and its correlation with business and consumers.

As a suggestion for further study, here are some possibilities and opportunities:

- Complementary study on the on-site view of consumers in the process of deciding and choosing products;
- Empirical study to measure the degree of incremental outlay consumers are willing to make for products that perform exactly the same function but have different visual and emotional aspects;
- Testing the feelings that most influence consumer decision-making, so that companies and designers can take them into account when developing projects, products, and solutions.

REFERENCES

BARDIN, L. **Análise de conteúdo**. Luís Antero Reto (Trad.). São Paulo: Edições, v. 70, 2016.

BATTISTELLA, C.; BIOTTO, G.; DE TONI, A. F. From design driven innovation to meaning strategy. **Management Decision**, v. 50, n. 4, p. 718-743, 2012.

BLIJLEVENS, J.; CREUSEN, M. EH; SCHOORMANS, J. PL. How consumers perceive product appearance: The identification of three product appearance attributes. **International Journal of Design**, v. 3, n. 3, p. 27-35, 2009.

BARNGROVER, M. The making of design champions. **Design Management Review**, v. 16, n. 2, p. 30-35, 2005.

BATRA, R.; SEIFERT, C.; BREI, D. (Ed.). **The psychology of design: Creating consumer appeal**. Abingdon: Routledge, 2015.

CHITTURI, R. Emotions by design: A consumer perspective. **International Journal of Design**, v. 3, n. 2, 2009.

CHITTURI, R. Design for Affect: A core competency for the 21st century. **NIM Marketing Intelligence Review**, v. 7, n. 2, p. 16, 2015.

CHITTURI, R. **Design, emotions, and willingness to pay**. In: Varadarajan, R. Innovation and Strategy. Bingley: Emerald Publishing Limited, 2018.

CREUSEN, M. EH; SCHOORMANS, J. PL. The different roles of product appearance in consumer choice. **Journal of Product Innovation Management**, v. 22, n. 1, p. 63-81, 2005.

DEMIR, E. The field of design and emotion: Concepts, arguments, tools, and current issues. **METU Journal of the Faculty of Architecture**, v. 25, n. 1, p. 135-152, 2008.

DRIESSEN, O. Design-driven innovation: at the intersection of design and business. **Business Review**, p. 61, mar., 2006.

FENKO, A.; VAN ROMPAY, T. JL. **Consumer-driven product design**. In: Methods in Consumer Research, v. 2. Sawston: Woodhead Publishing, 2018.

FONTGALLAND, I. L. A nova teoria do consumidor: uma análise acerca da abordagem da influência, da motivação e do status. **Revista Ibero-Americana de Humanidades, Ciências e Educação**, v. 7, n. 12, p. 220-246, 2021.

HOMBURG, C.; SCHWEMMLE, M.; KUEHNL, C. New product design: Concept, measurement, and consequences. **Journal of marketing**, v. 79, n. 3, p. 41-56, 2015.

JINDAL, R. P.; SARANGEE, K. R.; ECHAMBADI, R.; LEE, S. Designed to succeed: Dimensions of product design and their impact on market share. **Journal of Marketing**, v. 80, n. 4, p. 72-89, 2016.

HSU, C.-L.; CHEN, Y.-C.; YANG, T.-N.; LIN, W.-K.; LIU, Y.-H. Does product design matter? Exploring its influences in consumers' psychological responses and brand loyalty. **Information Technology & People**, v. 31, n. 3, p. 886-907, 2018.

KIM, S. H.; SIM, S. Y.; HAHM, Y. E. The Effects of Design Attributes on Other Attributes and Product Evaluation. **Seoul Journal of Business**, v. 20, n. 2, p. 1, 2014.

KOTLER, P.; KELLER, K. L. **Marketing para o século XXI**. In: Administração de marketing. 12. ed. São Paulo: Pearson Prentice Hall, 2006.

LADEIRA, W. J.; NARDI, V. A. M.; SANTINI, F. DE O.; JARDIM, W. C. Factors influencing visual attention: A meta-analysis. **Journal of Marketing Management**, v. 35, n. 17-18, p. 1710-1740, 2019.

LANDWEHR, J. R.; WENTZEL, D.; HERRMANN, A. The tipping point of design: How product design and brands interact to affect consumers' preferences. **Psychology & Marketing**, v. 29, n. 6, p. 422-433, 2012.

MARGOLIN, V. Design in history. **Design Issues**, v. 25, n. 2, p. 94-105, 2009.

MCKINSEY & COMPANY. **The Business Value of Design**, 2018.

MINAYO, M. C. S.; GUERRIERO, I. C. Zito. Reflexividade como éthos da pesquisa qualitativa. **Ciência & Saúde Coletiva**, v. 19, p. 1103-1112, 2014.

MONTEIRO, G. F. A. The use of design in business strategy: what's beneath the surface? **Design issues**, v. 37, n. 3, p. 78-88, 2021.

MORTATI, M.; VILLARI, B.; MAFFEI, S. **Design Capability for value creation**. In: 19th DMI: Academic Design Management Conference proceedings. Design Management Institute: London, 2014.

MOZOTA, B. B. **A theoretical model for Design in Management Science according to the paradigm shift of the Design profession**: from management as a constraint to management science as an opportunity. 1st International Design Management Symposium D2B, p. 16-19, Shanghai, 2006a.

MOZOTA, B. B. The four powers of design: a value model in design management. **Design Management Review**, v. 17, n. 2, p. 44-53, 2006b.

NAM, K. W.; CARNIE, B. W. **Design effectiveness**: Building customer satisfaction and loyalty through design. In: Proceedings of DRS 2014: Design's Big Debates. Umeå: Design Research Society, 2014

NOBLE, C. H.; KUMAR, M. Using product design strategically to create deeper consumer connections. **Business Horizons**, v. 51, n. 5, p. 441-450, 2008.

NOBLE, C. H.; KUMAR, M. Exploring the appeal of product design: A grounded, value-based model of key design elements and relationships. **Journal of Product Innovation Management**, v. 27, n. 5, p. 640-657, 2010.

NORMAN, D. A. **Emotional design: Why we love (or hate) everyday things**. Civitas Books, 2004. 287p.

NORMAN, D. A.; ORTONY, A. Designers and users: Two perspectives on emotion and design. **Symposium on foundations of interaction design**, p. 1-13, Ivrea, 2003.

PARK, H. Y.; CHANG, S. R. When and how brands affect importance of product attributes in consumer decision process. **European Journal of Marketing**, v. 56, n. 13, p. 1-25, 2022.

PARKMAN, I. The Informational Elements of Product Design Briefs: An Exploratory Investigation. **International Journal of Marketing & Business Communication**, v. 7, n. 1, p. 1, 2018.

PATROCINIO, G.; FILGUEIRAS, E.; NUNES, J. M. **A New Role for Design in the 21st Century from Operational to Tactical and Strategic**. In: Virtual and Augmented Reality for Architecture and Design. Boca Raton: CRC Press, 2022.

PAWAR, S.; NARANJE, S. A Study on Factors Influencing on Buying Behavior of Customers. **Research Journal**, 2016.

ROCCO, S.; SELINŠEK, A. The structure of design orientation and its relationship with market orientation. **Naše gospodarstvo/Our economy**, v. 65, n. 3, p. 50-62, 2019.

RUBERA, G. Design innovativeness and product sales' evolution. **Marketing Science**, v. 34, n. 1, p. 98-115, 2015.

STEVENS, J. S. **Design as a strategic resource: design's contributions to competitive advantage aligned with strategy models**. 2010. Tese (Doutorado em Engenharia de Manufatura). University of Cambridge, Cambridge, 2010.

VERGANTI, R. **Design driven innovation: changing the rules of competition by radically innovating what things mean**. Brighton: Harvard Business Press, 2009.